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**THE TURBULENT PATH TO SELFHOOD: A *BILDUNGSROMAN* ELEMENT
IN FERDINAND OYONO'S *HOUSEBOY* AND CHIMAMANDA NGOZI ADICHIE'S**

PURPLE HIBISCUS

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Abstract

The formative years often shape an individual's worldview and sense of self. The *bildungsroman*, a literary genre, offers profound insights into how the protagonist is shaped by their upbringing. This paper examines the intersections of childhood experiences, racial prejudice and familial dynamics that shape an individual's journey toward awareness, disillusionment, harm, and liberation. This paper examines how the formative years either set an individual on the path of self-awareness and disillusionment or the path of self-discovery and freedom through the analysis of the experiences of the protagonists in Ferdinand Oyono's *Houseboy* and Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus*. The paper draws from postcolonial and psychoanalytic theories to interrogate the two novels. The paper reveals the critical significance of early life experiences in shaping an individual's life trajectory. This study demonstrates that, while childhood experiences have a profound impact, individuals can still redefine and shape their own life path.

Keywords: *Bildungsroman*, Selfhood, Postcolonial theory, Psychoanalysis, Identity formation.

Introduction

There is a poignant line in one of John Keats' letters to his brother, George Keats, where he asks, "Do you not see how necessary a world of pains and troubles is to school an intelligence and make it a soul? A place where the heart must feel and suffer in a thousand diverse ways" (256). This sentiment, this insight into the didactic value of all experiences, may be said to form the essential theme of all works of literature. Nowhere is this more apparent than in the narrative sub-genre generally known as *bildungsroman*. It is largely a prose form, as seen in Charles Dickens's *David Copperfield*, Saul Bellow's *The Adventures of Augie March*, Ngugi wa Thiong'o's *Weep Not, Child*, Harper Lee's *To Kill a Mockingbird*, Sefi Atta's *Everything Good Will Come* and NoViolet Bulawayo's *We Need New Names*. Sharma describes the *bildungsroman* as:

A kind of novel that follows the growth and development of the hero or the heroine from childhood and youth to adulthood till he or she discovers his true identity. The term is derived from the combination of two words: The German word 'Bildung' which means 'formation' or 'development,' and the French 'roman' which means 'novel.' (23)

Additionally, Nnolim views *bildungsroman* as a novel tradition in which the protagonist embarks on a quest that is both physical and metaphorical (152). According to Nnolim, what determines whether a work fits into this genre is simply the transformation of the central character from a state of lack of self-awareness to self-discovery (153). Most often, the protagonist sets about a quest. Chukwuma asserts that "The quest is a search for the self, a realisation of the ego" (77). This quest can be an emotional, psychological, spiritual, cultural, and even moral desire of the protagonist to discover their place in society. The quest might also be for society to accept the

protagonist. Thus, a *bildungsroman* is essentially a story that portrays a protagonist's journey from ignorance and naivety to the attainment of knowledge and experience within a given society. There are many defining characteristics of the *bildungsroman*. One of the features, according to Christy, is that the protagonist experiences "a temperamental loss" (1236). Another feature of the *bildungsroman*, according to Upadhyay, is that its "hero is educated by his social environment rather than in an environment of an educational institution" (200). Thus, *bildungsroman* is also called the educational, initiation, apprentice or coming-of-age novel.

African writers often turn their literary lens to reflect the socio-economic and political realities of their society at a given time. While the thematic thrust of early African novels revolved around the colonial experience and its impact on the people as in the case of Oyono's *Houseboy*, later African writers turned their artistic lens to interrogate the postcolonial reality of African countries as in the case of Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus*. Falola notes that the colonial past and the global present are very much reflected in contemporary events in Africa (8). Okuyade equally argues that:

The cardinal thrust of African writing has been bi-focal from the very beginning. It is either geared towards decolonization or appraising the colonial aftermath. Colonialism and post-colonialism have become the twin sources that continue to inspire the African writer. (Changing Borders, 245)

This paper's central concern is to examine how childhood experiences, shaped by racial and family dynamics, intersect to influence an individual's self-perception and understanding of their place in society as depicted in Oyono's *Houseboy* and Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus*. These two novels reflect distinct regions and eras of Africa's socio-political history.

Review of Related Literature

Ferdinand Oyono's *Houseboy* and Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus* have both received extensive reviews from scholars reflecting diverse perspectives. Regarding Oyono's *Houseboy*, for instance, Charles Nnolim (1992) argues in his study of the novel against interpreting it primarily through satire, instead proposing an archetypal analysis of the protagonist to uncover the novel's underlying meanings.

Zuvalinyenga Dorcas (2013) examines the effects of colonial rule on the colonised in both British and French territories through the analysis of Oyono's *Houseboy* and two other African novels. Her study highlights how colonial powers employed education and religion as tools of subjugating African societies.

In a related study, Kalu Obasi Kalu (2018) critically examines the exploitative nature of French colonial government in Africa as portrayed in Oyono's *Houseboy* and *The Old Man and the Medal*. Kalu's paper also reveals that the French colonial government strategically replaced African cultural values and religious systems with those of France under the guise of friendship and civilisation.

Emmerencia Sih Beh and Walters Ncham Yong (2021) examine the oppression of women by the colonial authorities and African patriarchal structure in both Achebe's *Things Fall Apart* and Oyono's *Houseboy*. Their study highlights the intersection of forces of gendered and colonial subjugation that shape the experiences of characters in both novels.

The contribution of Peter Murage Ndambiri (2024) focuses on the maltreatment and marginalisation of domestic workers. Ndambiri's analysis of the *Houseboy* reveals the plight of

domestic servants and he calls for a more humane and cordial relationship between employers and domestic workers.

Turning to Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus*, Brenda Cooper (2008) examines the author's attempt to transcend the boundaries between Christian religiosity and ancestral spirituality. Cooper's analysis illustrates how Catholic belief systems often clash with African material culture and indigenous spirituality within the novel.

Similarly, Ann Ijeoma Ann Ibeku's (2015) paper, "Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus* and the Issue of Feminism in African Novel," examines *Purple Hibiscus* as a feminist text that confronts patriarchal dehumanisation of women. Ibeku's paper highlights the radical strategies women employ to resist and attain freedom from patriarchal oppression.

Ijeoma Chioma Anyachebelu's (2022) paper on Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus* reevaluates the character of Eugene Achike, challenging the common perception of him as a villain. She argues that Eugene's overbearing behaviour towards his family may be as a result of an underlying mental disorder, thus advocating for greater health awareness and urging people against hastily judging others.

Ariela Berkman-James' and Grant Andrews' (2025) paper slightly mirrors Anyachebelu's work by examining Eugene's psychological complexity. Their paper reinforces the connection between mental health and the intricate power dynamics at play depicted in the novel.

While these scholarly works on Oyono's *Houseboy* and Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus* have addressed various colonial, postcolonial, socio-cultural and political concerns, none have specifically examined the *bildungsroman* element in both novels. This present study seeks to fill

that gap by examining how external factors such as colonial and patriarchal oppression as well as religious tyranny, shape the protagonists' turbulent paths to self-awareness and growth.

Theoretical Framework

This paper is anchored on postcolonial theory and psychoanalysis as its theoretical frameworks. These two theories are particularly suited to the study because they provide critical insights into the external and internal dimensions of the protagonists' experiences in Ferdinand Oyono's *Houseboy* and Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus*. The *bildungsroman* genre traces both the social and psychological development of the protagonist. Postcolonial theory examines the external forces that undermine the characters' sense of self, while psychoanalysis explores their internal transformations – desires, feelings, emotional distress and paths towards either destruction or healing. Through postcolonial theory, this paper examines the historical, socio-political and cultural structures - such as colonialism, religious tyranny and patriarchy that shape the protagonists' worlds. Psychoanalysis, on the other hand, delves into the repressions, conflicts and emotional turmoil accompanying Toundi's and Kambili's turbulent journeys towards selfhood.

Postcolonial theory interrogates the colonial and postcolonial binary structures such as black/white, civilised/primitive, traditional/modern, and male/female, depicted in both novels. It provides a framework for analysing the power relations and family dynamics that shape the protagonists' experiences. This theory is particularly relevant in examining Toundi's transformative journey within the colonial setting of Cameroon and Kambili's struggle for self-definition under the authoritarian control of her father in postcolonial Nigeria.

The paper also draws on aspects of Freudian Psychoanalytic theory to examine the psychological impact of childhood experiences on the protagonists of the two novels. Psychoanalysis interrogates the behavioural and mental disorders that originate in the unconscious mind, revealing how suppressed desires and traumas shape individual behaviour. This theoretical framework helps to contextualise the psychological effects of the colonial and postcolonial socio-political and cultural experiences on the protagonists of both texts as they navigate the complex process of self-definition and growth.

The intersection of postcolonial theory and psychoanalysis thus provides nuanced insights into the turbulent process of self-realisation in Oyono's *Houseboy* and Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus* thereby highlighting the intricate negotiation between external forces of repression and the protagonists' internal psychological evolution.

Bildungsroman in Two African Novels

Colonialism and Struggle for Self-Realisation in Ferdinand Oyono's *Houseboy*

Houseboy is a novel by the Cameroonian author Ferdinand Oyono. The novel is written in the form of a diary by the protagonist Toundi Ondous. It is a coming-of-age novel about a young African boy in Dangan, Cameroon, during the colonial period. The events are seen from the perspective of the young houseboy and the story, in certain ways, is used to mock colonial rule and the brand of Christianity propagated by some colonial priests. Oyono's novel is a hilarious tale with tragic undertones.

Toundi flees home on the eve of his initiation ceremony thereby disrupting the cultural rite of passage of his transition from boyhood to manhood, instead opting to be a houseboy to the white Catholic priest, Father Gilbert. He prefers to remain a boy in the service of the white priest

rather than transiting to a man within his cultural milieu. According to Nnolim, Toundi abandons his parents and culture for the “paltry glitter of the white man’s world” (12). He desires to be part of the white man’s world and everything associated with it outweighs the importance of the rites of passage ceremony of his people. Toundi’s desire to embrace colonial Western values reflects the notion of mimicry. The protagonist of Oyono’s novel is the type of black man that Fanon asserts “wants to be like the white man” and who, he further argues, “admitted the unarguable superiority of the white man, and all his efforts are aimed at achieving a white existence” (178). The priest, Father Gilbert, throws little lumps of sugar to the children “like throwing corn to chickens” (10). But the boys are naïve to take note of the way the priest treats them.

The priest’s attitude toward Toundi highlights the ambivalent disposition of many white people towards Africans during colonial rule. The ambivalent attitude of demeaning and at the same time, nurturing is what Bhabha argues “raises affective and ethical issues connected with cultural differences and social discrimination – the problems of inclusion and exclusion, dignity and humiliation, respect and repudiation” (xvii). While he throws lumps of sugar to the boys, he also provides Toundi with “a pair of khaki shorts and a red jersey” (13). Toundi uses the first-person plural pronoun “we” when he talks about white people because he feels he is part of the white community since he resides with the white priest. His decision to never again submit to his father’s cane also marks just as Papa’s decision to abandon his father in Adichie’s *Purple Hibiscus*, his severance from his cultural roots. Toundi refuses to return to his village even when his parents die. Oyono’s *Houseboy*, according to Kalu, reflects Cameroonian society and the Cameroonians who, due to their strong faith in the French colonial system, became alienated from their people (53). Toundi begins his journey into the white world by learning how to read and write, a fundamental process in his development as a member of the white community he so much craves

to be part of. Through Father Gilbert, who acts as Toundi's tutor in his learning process, he studies the white community. He joyously confesses, "Everything I am I owe to Father Gilbert. He is my benefactor, and I am very fond of him" (14).

Father Gilbert's sudden death in an accident alters the course of his life. The new priest, Father Vandermayer, who is not particularly fond of Toundi, recommends him to the new Commandant. With the Commandant, he begins another phase of his *Bildung*, a very crucial one that will determine his fate later. The conversation between Toundi and the Commandant at their first meeting portrays the way some Europeans view Africans and it also equally exposes Toundi's naivety.

After he had looked at me for a long while, he asked me point-blank, if I were a thief.

'No, sir,' I answered.

'Why aren't you a thief?'

'Because I do not want to go to hell.'

He seemed taken aback by my answer. He tossed his head in disbelief.

'Where did you learn that?'

'I am a Christian, Sir.' I told him and proudly showed him the St. Christopher medal I wear around my neck.

'So, you are not a thief because you don't want to go to hell?'

'Yes, Sir.'

'What is it like, hell?'

'Well, Sir, it is flames and snakes and the Devil with horns. There is a picture of hell in my prayer book ... I ... I ... can show it to you.' (21)

To demonstrate that he has truly left the old ways behind, Toundi prefers to be called Joseph. As the Commandant's houseboy, he says, "The dog of the King is the King of dogs" (20). Toundi's declaration that he is the dog of the king exposes a poignant aspect of melancholia, which Freud asserts breaks out as an "extraordinary reduction in self-esteem" (345). Toundi's words equally reveal that he suffers from an identity crisis that stems from colonial oppression and internalised inferiority. Fanon notes that

When the Negro makes contact with the white world, a certain sensitizing action takes place. If his psychic structure is weak, one observes a collapse of the ego. The black man stops behaving as an *actional* person. The goal of his behaviour will be The Other (in the guise of the white man), for The Other alone can give him worth. (119)

Toundi's conversation with Sophie, a fellow Cameroonian, illustrates the extent to which he has drifted from his African roots. Sophie, who will later be the ground on which he is wrongfully accused, chides him, "You talk as if you weren't black We don't mean anything to them" (26-27) but Toundi has discarded what defines him as an African. Falola reveals that Europeans succeeded in getting Africans to adopt their culture through various means and institutions (4). Bhabha points out that the "barracks stands by the church which stands by the schoolroom" (119) in convincing the colonial subjects to embrace the ways of the white man and discard their African ways of life. In Oyono's *Houseboy*, the church, the barracks and the school constitute the various ways the colonial authority separates Africans from their cultural roots. Toundi continues his *Bildung* or education when he discovers that his great master, the Commandant, is uncircumcised. This discovery bemuses him greatly and somehow; it diminishes

the awe in which he holds the Commandant. Something snaps within him as he begins to gradually get disillusioned with the white community as his comment thereafter affirms:

No, it can't be true, I told myself, I couldn't have seen properly. A great chief like the Commandant is uncircumcised.

I was relieved by this discovery. It killed something inside me ... I knew I should never be frightened of the Commandant again. When he called me to bring his sandals, his voice sounded far off. I seemed to be hearing it for the first time. I wondered why I used to tremble in his presence.

My coolness surprised him. I took my time over what he told me to do. He shouted at me as he always did, but I did not move. (28-29)

This discovery transforms the way Toundi perceives the Commandant and the white world he represents. His respect for the Commandant is not just because he is a white man but because he is an older man, but culturally to Toundi, an uncircumcised grown-up male, no matter his status or achievement in life, is considered a child. The conversation between the commandant's wife and Toundi also reveals his gradual disillusionment with the Christian faith.

'You are a Christian, aren't you?'

'Yes, Madame, more or less.'

'What do you mean "more or less."?'

'Not very Christian, Madame. Christian because the priest poured water on my head and gave me a European name.'

'I can hardly credit what you are telling me now. The Commandant told me you were a very firm believer.'

‘We have to believe the white man’s stories – more or less.’ (56)

The European Community is not without blemish when Toundi discovers the Commandant’s wife's adulterous relationship with another European, M. Moreau, the brutality meted out to two Africans suspected of stealing from a white man and many other unfair treatments of Africans open his eyes to the ugly realities of life between the two communities in Dangan. In his diary, he notes, “How wretched we are I was so upset by what I had seen. There are some things it is better never to see. Once you have seen them, you can never stop living through them over and over again. I don’t think I shall ever forget what I have seen.” (77)

The summary at the back of the novel states clearly why the white community conspired to do away with him. In his bid to advance and improve himself, he studies his “new world closely – too closely” for their comfort. Toundi’s knowledge of the secrets and ways of life of the white community makes him a threat. Baklu, the laundry boy, forebodingly tells Toundi after he discovers some used condoms, “I suppose you’ve upset Madame Your broom reached a bit too far A white woman just can’t let her houseboy find things like that” (89). Also, Kalisia, the chambermaid to the Roberts, a black woman well-versed in the ways of white people, warns Toundi about the danger of knowing too much about his new world. She tells him to flee before the full weight of the anger of the white community comes hard on him

“If I were in your place... I’d go now before the river swallowed me up altogether.

Our ancestors used to say you must escape when the water is still only up to the knees I was saying though, that because you know all their business, while you are still here, they can never forgive you for that.... If I were in your shoes, I

swear I'd go right away ... I wouldn't even wait for my month's wages.' (100-101)

Toundi disregards Kalisia advice and subsequently faces false accusations, arrest and torture for allegedly being Sophie's lover and accomplice who absconds with her master's money. Fanon notes that white people have a way of blaming a black person for their moral depravity. He asserts that the "collective guilt is borne by what is conventionally called the scapegoat. Now the scapegoat for white society ... is supplied by the negro" (150) because, as he states further the "Negro is the symbol of sin" (153). Toundi becomes the scapegoat of the white community because his broom stretches too far into their many depravities. It eventually dawns on Toundi to flee the animosity of the white people from his hospital bed to Spanish Guinea, but by then, it is too late. He has already been broken physically and emotionally by the very world to which he tries passionately to belong. On his deathbed in Spanish Guinea, away from Dangan, everything becomes clear to him. He tells the unnamed boy that he hands his packet containing his diary that:

"Brother," he said. "Brother, what are we? What are we, black men who are French?" His voice grew bitter. I had never asked myself the question. I was young then and thoughtless. I felt myself grow stupid.

"You see, brother," he went on, "I'm finished ...they've got me Still I'm glad I'm dying well away from where they are.... I am from the Cameroons, my friend, I'm a Maka ... I'd have old bones if I'd been good and stayed at home in the village." (4)

Toundi's fascination with the white world ends in regret when he eventually understands the white community. His journey of self-discovery and self-advancement eventually culminated in his realisation that the world he abhorred as a boy - the world of his people - was what he should have settled for not the elusive white world he had opted for. On his deathbed, away from Dangan, his *Bildung* or education tragically comes to an end.

From Silence to Sound: The Rocky Path to Selfhood in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus*

Another African novel that fits into the *bildungsroman* genre is *Purple Hibiscus* by Nigerian writer Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie. The event of the novel is seen through the eyes of a thirteen-year-old Kambili, growing up under a tyrannical religious father during a period of military dictatorship in Nigeria. It shows the trajectory of the growth of the female protagonist, Kambili, the narrator, from a "past...when Jaja and Mama and I spoke more with our spirits than with our lips" (15) to when she and her brother subtly begin to challenge their father's tyrannical hold on the family. According to Okuyade, the novel highlights the struggle of the protagonist and her brother "to define themselves, beyond the stiffened, and funless world their Calvinistic father has fashioned for them" (Changing Borders, 246). The novel begins on a Palm Sunday when "things started to fall apart" because Jaja refuses to take communion, prompting Papa to hurl his "heavy missal across the room and broke the figurines on the *étagère*" (3). Okuyade observes that this Palm Sunday incident marks the moment when the foundation of Papa's family "begins to crumble and everything about him begins to have a downward trajectory" (Changing Borders, 254). Jaja's refusal to take communion and his defiance of his father, Eugene Achike, whom the narrator refers to as Papa. This incident signals the gradual erosion of Papa's authoritarian hold on his family.

Just like the colonial authority represented by the Commandant, which subjugates Toundi, Papa also emotionally and physically subjugates his family members, leading to the manifestation of melancholia which, according to Freud, is a “profound painful depression, loss of interest in the outside world ... the inhibition of any kind of performance” (33) as reflected in Kambili. But after travelling to Nsukka, Jaja begins to do what no member of the family has ever done before, such as leaving the table before Papa says the prayer after the meal. According to the narrator, Jaja’s attitude defies Papa’s authority: “This had never happened before in my entire life, never” (14). Jaja transforms from the boy who keeps his lips tight to the one who asserts his preference and Kambili observes at the dinner table that things begin to fall apart as “a shadow that had been in Jaja’s eyes. Fear. It had left Jaja’s eyes and entered Papa’s” (13). Even Mama is not ready to replace the figurines that have always been her object of solace, a kind of refuge when she receives the ugly side of her husband. She is no longer ready to direct her suppressed emotion to the figurines. The binary family dynamics between Papa and his wife and children begin to crumble slowly but steadily.

The novel, of course, begins in media res, and the narrator goes back to a period before Palm Sunday, before “Things started to fall apart at home when my brother, Jaja, did not go to communion” (1), and Papa throws a missal that breaks the figurines through flashback. Before Palm Sunday, Papa’s authority within his homestead was absolute, the same way the Commandant wields complete control over Toundi. His wife and children cannot question his authority. His oppressive grip on his family makes the wife and children afraid to express their thoughts and desires openly. As a result, they speak more through silence than words. They develop a kind of eye contact as a way of communicating with one another. Kambili describes the suffocating situation at home:

We went upstairs to change, Jaja, Mama and I. Our steps on the stairs were as measured and silent as our Sundays: the silence of waiting until Papa was done with his siesta so we could have lunch; the silence of reflection time, when Papa gave us a scripture passage or a book by one of the early church fathers to read and meditate on; silence of evening rosary; the silence of driving to the church for benediction afterwards. (31)

Papa provides well for his wife and children so they lack nothing but he undermines their ability to act and talk freely. The house in Enugu is more like a prison to the children and their mother. Eugene possesses two starkly different personalities. He is philanthropic, deeply religious, a kind family man to the public but a complete tyrant at home to his family members. Even when he encourages the editor of his newspaper, Ade Coker, to speak out against injustice in society, at home, he subjects his family to a state of near-complete paralysis of the mouth. Ade Coker observes that his publisher's children are always quiet and his remark is profoundly significant: "Imagine what the Standard would be if we were all quiet" (58). This reveals Papa's paradoxical disposition as he desires his newspaper to serve as a vocal critic of government excesses. Yet, his wife and children cannot speak about his own excesses. His overbearing attitude toward his wife and children effectively stifles their ability to speak out against his dictatorial nature. This is especially evident in Kambili, who maintains a striking silence among her classmates but speaks only to her close friend, Ezinne. She hardly interacts with her classmates. Kambili's behaviour illustrates Freud's concept of melancholia, where the individual exhibits a loss of interest in external relationships (343). Papa's oppressive disposition weighs down on Kambili socially and psychologically. Later in Nsukka, her cousin Amaka considers her abnormal because she is

socially and emotionally withdrawn from others. The novel is viewed as a *bildungsroman* because it chronicles Kambili's transformation from a timid person to an assertive individual.

The quest to find her voice and also be herself is at the heart of the novel. She undergoes her *Bildung* or learning process when she travels with her brother to visit their aunt, a lecturer, at Nsukka. To Okuyade, Nsukka is not just where the narrator's aunt resides but a "symbol of liberty" (Weaving Memories, 152). Nsukka is, no doubt, a liberating space for the protagonist and her brother to define themselves. It is where Kambili finds her voice and comes into her own. She affirms this at the beginning of the novel:

Until Nsukka. Nsukka started it all; Aunty Ifeoma's little garden next to the verandah of her flat in Nsukka began to lift the silence. Jaja's defiance seemed to me like Aunty Ifeoma's experimental purple hibiscus: rare, fragrant with the undertones of freedom, a different kind of freedom from the one the crowds waving green leaves chanted at Government Square after the coup. A freedom to be, to do. But my memories did not start at Nsukka. They started before when all the hibiscuses in our front yard were a startling red. (15-16)

The visit to Aunty Ifeoma's household is significant in the lives of Kambili and Jaja as they are exposed to a more liberal and unconventional environment that challenges their rigid and stifling upbringing. Through their interaction with their aunt and her children, they begin to question the strict rules imposed by their father and they slowly start to develop a more independent and critical mindset. Kambili observes that "Papa stared at Jaja, then at me, shaking his head slowly as if we had somehow changed colour" (189). The children have been exposed to the fact that hibiscus can equally be purple. Kambili and Jaja have both transcended the liminal space of when

the “hibiscuses ... were a startling red,” a time when they and their mother are unable to stand up to the excesses of Papa. The purple hibiscus is a metaphor for freedom, a kind of liberation from Papa’s tyrannical grip on the family. Cooper equates the image of “the purple hibiscus with language, with finding voice out of silence” (124) for Kambili and Jaja.

At the heart of the *bildungsroman* is the environment, as well as the physical and psychological changes that the protagonist undergoes. The change heralds the protagonist making a fundamental decision. Nsukka presents this idea in *Purple Hibiscus* just as Spanish Guinea offers it to Toundi. Auntie Ifeoma’s house at Nsukka liberates Kambili and Jaja from the stifling colonial-like grip of their father since, as Dube puts it, “Papa Eugene embodies colonial epistemic violence” (228) because, just as in the case of the subjugation of Toundi in Oyono’s *Houseboy* by the representative of the colonial authority, Papa subjugates his wife and children. The situation at Auntie Ifeoma’s struggling household in Nsukka is in sharp contrast to the situation in Enugu where there is an abundance of nearly all the good things of life. Kambili and her brother are exposed to an entirely different way of life at Nsukka. Kambili says:

I looked down at the jollof rice, fried plantains, and half of a drumstick on my plate and tried to concentrate, tried to get the food down. The plates too were mismatched. Chima and Obiora used plastic ones while the rest of us had plain glass plates, bereft of dainty flowers or silver lines. Laughter floated over my head. Words spurted from everyone, often not seeking and not getting any response. We always spoke with a purpose back at home, especially at the table, but my cousins seemed to simply speak and speak and speak. (119-120)

The *bildungsroman* is also known as the apprentice story or the story of initiation. In Oyono's *Houseboy*, we find that idea in Toundi's mentorship under Father Gilbert and later Commandant Robert. Apprenticeship and mentoring are a vital part of any *Bildung* or learning process. The protagonist needs a mentor for the process that will lead to self-discovery, maturity and the experience required to find their proper place in society. In *Purple Hibiscus*, Mama is too weak to serve as a mentor to her daughter because she needs mentoring herself. Therefore, Aunty Ifeoma acts as a mentor to Kambili, along with Amaka and Father Amadi. Stan and Sahi assert that Aunty Ifeoma is "crucial to Kambili's recuperation and resistance. Her home becomes a haven for Kambili, providing an alternative setting where open dialogue and critical thinking are welcomed" (70). Aunty Ifeoma counters Papa's designation of Igbo traditional religion and cultural practices as primitive and barbaric offering Kambili and Jaja a better understanding of their grandfather's religious practices and cultural heritage. She corrects her niece for referring to Papa-Nnukwu as a 'pagan' thereby challenging Papa's categorisation of African indigenous religion and culture practices as barbaric, which reflects his lingering colonial mentality.

When Kambili asks, "How can Our Lady intercede on behalf of a heathen, Aunty?" (164), Aunty Ifeoma says that her father is a traditionalist, not a heathen. She likens the Catholic saying of the rosary to Papa-Nnukwu's *itu-nzu*, his declaration of innocence in the morning. She wakes Kambili to listen to her grandfather saying *itu-nzu* early in the morning when the old man prays even for his son who has abandoned him because he refused to leave the ways of his ancestors. This alters the way Kambili perceives her grandfather. Kambili returns to Enugu after the holiday at Nsukka a changed person. In school unlike before Nsukka, she says: "I joined the group of girls on the volleyball field on the second day of school. I did not hear the whisper of "backyard snob"

or the ridiculing laughter. I did not notice the amused pinches they gave one another. I stood waiting with my hands clasped until I was picked” (202).

Events take a spiral dimension as Ade Coker is assassinated; Kambili is beaten to a coma by Papa because of her defiant clinging to Papa-Nnukwu’s painting given to her by Amaka. On her hospital bed where she lies recuperating, Kambili tells her mother to call Auntie Ifeoma and she equally resolves to leave the hospital not for home but for Nsukka. Mama’s repressed rage, fueled by years of Papa’s physical and emotional assault on her and the children, ultimately culminates in her killing her husband. She returns to Nsukka because “it could free something deep inside your belly that would rise to your throat and come out as a freedom song” (291). It is where her transition from a timid young girl to a confident young adult begins.

At the end of the novel, Kambili is a confident and self-assured individual, overseeing her own affairs as well as those of Jaja and Mama. Her ability to make decisions regarding her loved ones and herself shows her remarkable growth and maturity. Kambili’s story serves as a powerful testament to the human ability to overcome personal adversity in the fraught journey towards growth, self-discovery and ultimately, freedom.

Conclusion

The *bildungsroman* is indicative of the journey of discovery that every human being undertakes. Oyono’s *Houseboy* is about the growing-up years of an African boy during the colonial era while in Adichie’s *Purple Hibiscus*, the artistic lens turns to the journey of discovery of a young African girl in post-colonial Africa. This paper demonstrated the profound impact of childhood and adolescence on an individual’s future, highlighting how the intersection of racial prejudice and family dynamics defines an individual’s perception of self and the world. Through the experience of Oyono’s protagonist, the paper illustrates the notion that Africans should never

completely abandon cultural values and norms of their community. In Adichie's novel, the paper highlights the capability of an individual to overcome childhood adversities and chart a better future for themselves.

The formative years of the protagonists in both novels illustrate how oppression and adversity can profoundly either stifle an individual's potential or empower their resilience. Through the analysis of Oyono's *Houseboy* and Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus*, this paper demonstrates that childhood experiences can exert a profound and enduring influence in shaping an individual. The paper concludes that, despite the impact of early life experiences, individuals possess the ability to rise above those experiences and shape their future course.

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